

AN ECONOMIC ANALYSIS OF PRODUCTION OF GUAVA IN PUNE DISTRICT OF MAHARASHTRA STATE

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Abstract

Pune district of Maharashtra state is known for its fruit production. Guava is an important fruit grown in Pune district. The present study has been made to measure the economic performance of the guava crop of 96 farmers from 8 villages in Pune district. The primary data was collected by personal interview with survey method using a properly planned and pre-tested schedule. The timetable detailing the physical inputs, cost of various expenditures, and returns for the 2020-21 crop year was received. Standard cost concepts such as Cost A, Cost B and Cost C were used to calculate the cost of cultivation of guava crop. Various statistical tools and techniques were used in analysing the data. The results revealed that the establishment cost per hectare of guava orchard was ₹462449.18 and per hectare cost of cultivation was ₹520277.94. The yield from one hectare of guava orchard was observed to be 189.21 quintals while the gross income was ₹1050953.02 and the net profit obtained by farmer was ₹530675.08. The B:C ratio was seen to be 2.02 which indicated that guava crop is profitable.

Key words: Establishment cost, Input utilization, Benefit cost ratio, Net profit

Introduction

Guava (*Psidium guajava* L.) belongs to the genera *Psidium* of the family Myrtaceae. Since the 17th century, guava has gained a place in the important cultivated fruit crops. In India in the states viz. Uttar Pradesh, Madhya Pradesh, Karnataka, Maharashtra, West Bengal, Orissa and Tripura guava cultivation has become extremely successful. The guava production in India during financial year 2021 was 4582.30 ('000 Metric Tonnes) and area under guava cultivation was 308.09 ('000 Hectares), while the total guava production in Maharashtra was 129.75 ('000 Metric tonne). (Source: National Horticulture Board Database 2021). Important varieties of guava grown in Maharashtra are VNR, Pink Taiwan, Red Gujarat, Sardar, Allahabad Safeda, G.Vilas, etc.

Pune district is one of the important districts of Maharashtra where guava is grown. The district is identified as Agricultural Export Zone for grapes, pomegranate and floriculture. Guava cultivation in this district is seen to be increasing rapidly. 1589.55 hectare land in Pune district is under Guava cultivation as on 10 January 2022. Out of this 116 hectares is in Baramati tehsil and 420 hectares is in Indapur tehsil which were considered in the study. Guava gives good economic returns to the farmer and also does not require substantially more inputs like other fruits such as grapes and pomegranate. As Guava is emerging as an important crop that will help in increase of income due to its wide adaptability, thus an effort was made in economics of guava production.

Objective

To estimate per ha cost, returns and profitability of guava crop.

Materials and Methods

Multistage sampling design was adopted in selection of Pune district, tehsils, villages and Guava growers. Pune district of Maharashtra state was purposively selected for the study in the first stage. In the second stage from Pune district, two tehsils viz. Baramati and Indapur were chosen. In third stage, four villages each from the two tehsils namely Katewadi, Malegaon, Pimpali Limtek and Undavadi Kade Pathar from Baramati tehsil and Kalas, Shelgaon, Warkute Kh. and Nimgaon Ketaki from Indapur tehsil were selected randomly. In the last stage to collect data on production, cost, returns and other factors, 12 farmers from each village i.e. total 96 guava growers were chosen. The information was gathered for the fiscal year 2020-21. The data

Table 1: Cost of establishment of guava orchard

Sr. No.	Name of Operations	Amount (₹/Ha)	Per cent
1.	Land Preparation and layout	15777.40	3.41
2.	Digging of pits	11245.81	2.43
3.	Cost of plants	186521.10	40.33
4.	Permanent fencing	20000.00	4.32

was gathered by survey method by interviewing the farmers using a properly planned and pre-tested schedule. The cost, return and profitability in guava production was achieved by application of tabular analysis of standard cost concepts viz. cost-A, cost-B and cost-C. It is comprised of percentage, B:C ratio, output input ratio and arithmetic mean. To analyze the economics of production, it is essential to study the establishment cost as well as cost of cultivation.

Results and discussion**Cost, Returns and Profitability of Guava**

The analysis and calculating of cost, returns and profitability of guava crop requires inclusion of establishment cost of orchard along with cost of cultivation. The cost of establishment was presented in table 1.

Guava is a perennial crop that once planted, continues to produce fruit for number of years. Therefore, good orchard establishment is better for future crop income potential. The initial investment on land preparation, marking of lines, digging of pits, fencing, cleaning, plantation, drip set installation, fertigation, gap filing, pruning, plant protection and irrigation cost were all included in the cost of starting a guava orchard in that area. In the context of the study, the establishment cost was determined taking into account the initial expenses. Based on accepted cost principles, the average cost per hectare to create an orchard was calculated. The guava orchard establishment cost per hectare was ₹462449.18. Planting material accounted for highest part in establishing an orchard. The cost of planting material was 40.33 per cent of the total establishment cost. It was followed by other costs. The cost of land preparation includes ploughing, harrowing, cleaning and amount required for layout of orchard. It was ₹ 15777.40 (3.41 per cent). For digging of pits, ₹11245.81 (2.43) was needed. Installation of drip set required ₹75727.07 (16.38 per cent). Fertigation includes FYM, Poultry manure and fertilizers, out of which manure accounted for ₹47195.65 (10.21 per cent) per cent and all fertilizers accounted ₹24853.60 (5.37 per cent) of the total cost of establishment. Irrigation charges were ₹6260.13 (1.36 per cent). The inter-cultivation charges included weeding charges, pruning, staking and deflowering which were ₹15851.44 (3.43 per cent). The interest on working capital was ₹53202.12. The annual cost of establishment for one hectare guava orchard was ₹46244.91.

5.	Irrigation cost	6260.13	1.36
6.	Installation of drip set	75727.07	16.38
7.	Manures	47195.65	10.21
8.	Fertilizers	24853.60	5.37
9.	Inter cultivation	15851.44	3.43
10.	Plant protection	5814.86	1.26
11.	Interest on working capital @ 13per cent	53202.12	11.50
	Total Establishment Cost	462449.18	100
	Annual Establishment Cost	46244.91	

Per hectare resources utilization pattern

The utilization pattern of various resources per hectare of land is shown in table 2. The hired male requirement was 19.51 per ha. And that of hired female was 69.63 per ha. The family male labour requirement was 71.28 days per ha and family female days required were 21.27. Bullock labour days and machine hours required were 0.05 and 32.61 respectively. Cow dung manure requirement for 1 hectare was 31.55 ton and poultry manure requirement was 13.70

bags i.e. 685 kg's per ha. Nitrogen, Phosphorous and Potassium required per ha were 458.16 kg, 248.01 kg and 588.39 kg respectively. Plant protection included fungicides, bactericides, pesticides and foams and carry bags for bagging. The plant protection required was 5.34 lit pesticides, 2.53 kg fungicides/bactericides and 21348.7 foams and bags for a hectare. The irrigation charges were calculated to be ₹23668.28.

Table 2: Per hectare resources utilization pattern in Guava cultivation

Sr. no.	Particulars	Unit/ha	Quantity
	INPUT		
1.	Hired human labour	man days	
a.	Male		19.51
b.	Female		69.63
2.	Family human labour	man days	
a.	Male		71.28
b.	Female		21.27
3.	Bullock labour	pair days	0.05
4.	Machine labour	hours	32.61
5.	Manures		
a.	Cow dung manure	ton	31.55
b.	Poultry manure	bags	13.70
6.	Fertilizer		
a.	N	kg	458.16
b.	P	kg	248.01
c.	K	kg	588.39
7.	Plant Protection		
a.	Pesticides	kg/lit	5.34
b.	Fungicides/Bactericides	kg/lit	2.53
c.	Foam and Bag	no.	21348.70
9.	Irrigation charges	₹	23668.28

Per Hectare Cost of Cultivation of Guava

The cost of cultivation of guava per hectare is calculated in table 3. From the table it is evident that, per hectare cost of cultivation of Guava was ₹520277.94 (Cost C). The share of Cost A and Cost B in the cost of cultivation was 62.34 per cent and 96.52 per cent respectively. Different items were considered in calculating cost of cultivation which were hired and family labour, bullock labour, machine labour, manures, fertilizers, plant protection chemicals etc. The rental value of land accounted for the highest per cent in cost C i.e. 31.60 per cent, it was followed by plant protection i.e. 15.19 per cent. This was followed by Cow dung manure which accounted for 12.13 per cent. The land revenue was ₹ 81 (0.02). The interest on

working capital was computed by taking the summation of items up to incidental charges except the land revenue. The interest on working capital was 30892.85 (5.94 per cent). The depreciation was calculated on capital assets including tractor and electric motor. It was ₹9502.21 (1.83 per cent). The incidental charges were ₹3000 (0.58 per cent). The rental value of land was ₹164430.84 which accounted for 31.60 per cent of cost of cultivation. The cost A was computed to be ₹324358.24 and Cost B ₹502170.01. The fertilizers summed up were 7.24 per cent of cost C. The hired male and female labour together was 5.12 per cent of cost C and Family male and female labour was total 3.48 per cent. The bullock labour and machine labour accounted for 0.05 and 4.99 per cent of total cost of cultivation.

Table 3: Per hectare cost of cultivation of guava crop

Sr. No.	Particulars	Amount (₹)	Per cent
1.	Hired human labour		
a.	Male labour	7695.19	1.48
b.	Female labour	18963.09	3.64
2.	Machine labour	25940.99	4.99
3.	Bullock labour	278.52	0.05
4.	Manure		
a.	Cow dung manure	63095	12.13
b.	Poultry manure	1961.96	0.38
5.	Fertilizer		
a.	N	6973.19	1.34

b.	P	17050.69	3.28
c.	K	13627.11	2.62
6.	Plant protection	79051.53	15.19
7.	Land revenue and other taxes	81.00	0.02
8.	Incidental charges	3000.00	0.58
9.	Interest on working capital @ 13 per cent	30892.85	5.94
10.	Annual establishment cost	46244.91	8.89
11.	Depreciation on capital assets @ 10 per cent	9502.21	1.83
12.	Cost-A (Σ 1 to11)	324358.24	62.34
13.	Rental value of land	164430.84	31.60
14.	Interest on fixed capital @ 10 per cent	13380.93	2.57
15.	Cost-B (Σ 12 to14)	502170.01	96.52
16.	Family human labour		
a.	Male labour	12340.04	2.37
b.	Female labour	5767.89	1.11
17.	Cost-C (Σ 15 to16)	520277.94	100
18.	Supervision charges @ 10 per cent Cost A	32435.82	6.23

Per hectare profitability of Guava crop

The per-hectare total cost, total production, and return from Guava crop are shown in table 4 along with several levels of cost, such as Cost-A, Cost-B, and Cost-C, which were total values. According to the table, average Guava production per hectare was 189.21 quintal, and profits from Guava cultivation were ₹561964.32. Total cultivation costs were ₹488988.70, and the per-quintal cost of production was ₹2749.74. Cost-A and Cost-B contributed ₹324358.24 and ₹502170.01 to Cost-C, respectively, for guava.

The profit, which was calculated at a specific cost level, is also shown in table 4. The Guava farm's expected farm business income, or (gross return-cost A), was ₹726594.78. The income from family labour, i.e. (gross return- cost-B) was calculated to be ₹548783.01. The Net income which was Gross return minus Cost-C was ₹530675.08 for guava orchard. The Benefit Cost ratio was computed from the data in the table by dividing Gross returns by Cost-C and it arrived to be 2.02. From the obtained Benefit cost ratio, it is clear that the guava crop is profitable in the study area considered.

Table 4: Per hectare profitability of guava crop

Sr. no.	Particulars	Physical unit	Physical quantity (per/ha)	Amount (₹/Ha)
1.	Return from main produce	quintal	189.21	1050953.02
2.	Return from by produce		-	-
3.	Gross return (Σ 1 to 2)		189.21	1050953.02
4.	Cost-A			324358.24
5.	Cost-B			502170.01
6.	Cost-C			520277.94
7.	Farm business income (Gross return minus Cost-A)			726594.78
8.	Family labour income (Gross return minus Cost -B)			548783.01
9.	Net Profit (Gross return minus Cost-C)			530675.08
10.	Benefit- Cost ratio (Gross return divided by Cost- C)			2.02
11.	Per quintal cost of production (Cost-C minus by produce value divided by main produce quantity)			2749.74

Conclusion

The above results clearly indicate that guava cultivation is an economically practicable enterprise. The per hectare cost of establishment of guava orchard which included elements such as land preparation, digging of pits, fencing, etc. was ₹462449.18 and annual establishment cost was ₹46244.91. Per hectare hired male requirement was 19.51 man days, hired female requirement was 69.63 man days and family male & family female labour was 71.28 man days and 21.27 man days respectively. Per hectare machine labour utilized was 32.61 hours and bullock labour was 0.05 days. The Nitrogen, Phosphorous and Potassium utilization requirement was 458.16 kg, 248.01 kg and 588.39 kg respectively. Cow dung manure was required for guava production at an extent of 31.55 tonnes for one hectare and poultry manure was required to the extent of 13.70 bags i.e.685 kg. The foams and bags play an important place in protection of fruits and their proper development. The foams and

bags requirement was 21348.70 per ha. Per hectare cost of cultivation was ₹520277.94 i.e. Cost-C. The Cost A was ₹324358.24 and Cost B was ₹502170.01. The returns obtained from a hectare were 189.21 quintal fruits accounting ₹1050953.02. Per hectare farm business income obtained was ₹726594.78; family labour income obtained was ₹548783.01. The Net Profit obtained was ₹530675.08 and B:C ratio was 2.02. The Benefit cost ratio clearly indicates that guava crop is profitable.

References

1. Kumar, R., Kumar, N., Dhillon, A., Bishnoi, D.K., Kavita. & Malik, A.K. (2019). Economic analysis of guava (*Psidium guajava L.*) in Sonapat District of Haryana. *Economics Affairs*. 64 (4), 747-752.
2. Kumbhar, J.S., Pawar, P.P., Patole, S.D., & Gawali, A.S. (2014). Economics of production and marketing of guava in

- Maharashtra. *International Journal of Agriculture Sciences*. 10 (2), 592-599.
3. **Meena, M. (2016).** *Economic Analysis of guava cultivation (Psidium guajava L.) in Sawai Madhopur District Of Rajasthan (Master's Thesis)*. Swami Keshawanand Rajasthan Agricultural University, Bikaner.
 4. **Pokharkar, V.G., Sangle, S.A. & Kulkarni, A.R. (2016).** Economics of production and marketing of guava in western Maharashtra. *International Research Journal of Agricultural Economics and Statistics*. 7(2), 234-242.
 5. **Sain, V., Luhach, V.P., Mehla, M.S. & Jyoti V. (2013).** Economic Analysis of guava production in Haryana. *IOSR Journal of Agriculture and Veterinary Sciences*. 5 (5), 7-11.
 6. **Sandhya Kiran, M. (1997).** *Economic analysis of Guava orchards in Anantpur district of Andhra Pradesh (Master's Thesis)*. Acharya N.G. Ranga Agricultural University, Tirupati.
 7. **Byresh, T. (2007).** *Comparative Economics of Local and Improved Variety of guava orchards in Dharwad district of Karnataka (Master's Thesis)*. University of Agricultural Sciences.